

The Implementation of the CSR Program as an Effort to Improve the Environmental Quality through the Empowerment of Scavengers

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Abstract

*This study aims to analyze and explain how the CSR implementation carried out by PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) through the Empowerment of Scavengers' activities in South Tangerang. The method used in this study is a qualitative method with a single case study design. The uniqueness of the CSR program carried out by PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) is the implementation of CSR program that refers to environmental issues and integrated empowerment of scavengers. The results of the study show that: **firstly**, the CSR program implemented by PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) is a commitment to fulfill the company's moral obligations, strengthen reputation, as a form of company compliance with the prevailing laws and regulations, as well as the company's steps to maintain sustainable business, **secondly**, CSR programs refer to the triple bottom line concept i.e. achieving profit by realizing the Recycling Business Unit (RBU) and Formation, achieving people by empowering through training in professional waste management, achieving the planet with the proper waste management process so that the volume of waste and environmental pollution can be reduced, **thirdly**, CSR programs have an impact on the community, this is shown by the award from the Ministry of Environment and Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia in the category of "Award of Producer Initiative in Waste Reduction". Based on the findings of the study, the researcher suggests that companies consider the following: **firstly**, increasing community participation in CSR programs is very important. The future PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) needs to design CSR programs collaboratively by involving wider stakeholders, not only scavengers but also the general public, **secondly**, developing communication models and strategies that are more targeted at the general public so that the success of CSR programs can be broader. In additions, it is necessary to add various communication and socialization media that can expand the implementation of CSR, and **thirdly**, maintaining the consistency of the existence of cooperatives, so that these cooperatives can be more developed in accelerating the economic welfare of members, especially scavengers.*

Key Words: CSR, Environment, Empowerment & Scavengers

1. INTRODUCTION

The greater the population, the bigger the volume of waste. Recently, the waste is produced from various human activities that come from the industry, agriculture, household waste, markets, etc. The problem is that there is increasing domestic waste, which is one of the household activities that leaves a dominant or community waste. Increasing domestic waste is in line with the physical development, facilities, and infrastructure. As a result of this pollution, the environmental balance is disturbed, for example, the infectious diseases, slums and etc.

South Tangerang as one of the supporting cities in Jakarta is certainly not free from the waste problem. This is as reported by news.metrotvnews.com that there is an increase in consumption of South Tangerang residents during Ramadan affecting the volume of household waste. The number of household waste increases by 10 percent or 275 tons per day. To overcome this problem, the South Tangerang City Government took anticipatory steps related to increased volume. One of them is by increasing the transportation of waste to the garbage disposal of Cipeucang. "Usually we transport 250 tons of garbage every day. During fasting, it becomes around 275 tons per day," he explained. Head of the Waste Transportation and Collection Section Environment Agency of South Tangerang Wisman Syah said that the increase in household waste during Ramadan is common (<http://news.metrotvnews.com>).

To overcome this waste problem, it is certainly not just the responsibility of the government, but the community, industry players, and other stakeholders. Collective awareness is the key to the solution to this waste problem. In addition, the contribution of the industry to take responsibility for waste is also important. This is because the industry is also one of the parties that are suppliers of the waste.

Understanding these conditions, PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) is concerned to hold a Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) program with the concept of empowering scavengers. The CSR program activities carried out by PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group), namely empowerment of scavengers, manufacturing scavenger cooperatives, as well as creating a container of management business for plastic waste recycling/ Recycling Business Unit (RBU) which has now been renamed Reksa Buana Utama which

has company operational standards and safety concerns work for the scavengers who are empowered. The CSR program through empowerment of scavengers is located on Jl. Cipeucang Raya, RT. 003/ RW. 003, Kademangan, Setu, South Tangerang. This CSR program is an effort to preserve the environment and improve the quality of life of the people. This is an effort to achieve the company's goals so that they can have a sustainable impact.

The Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a company committed to contributing to the sustainable economic development by paying attention to corporate social responsibility and focusing on the balance between attention to economic, social and environmental aspects. But not all companies realize the importance of carrying out this CSR activity with the right implementation. This CSR practice is considered to make the big costs for companies. Therefore many middle-class companies do not carry out CSR activities because they still do not understand the benefits gained from managing CSR programs.

In Indonesia CSR programs have been regulated in laws and regulations Article 15 letter (b) of Law no.25 of 2007 and Article 74 of Law no.40 of 2007. The law essentially explains that the company must carry out its corporate social responsibilities. However, essentially the company should carry out CSR programs. The CSR is a commitment of the company to contribute to sustainable economic development by paying attention to corporate social responsibility and focusing on the balance between attention to economic, social and environmental aspects.

Although many companies have carried out CSR activities, they have not provided benefits to the community. This is because CSR is still used as a tool to communicate the image and reputation of the company to the public so that it is viewed well by its stakeholders. In fact, the image and reputation are the impact of CSR programs and not the main goal of CSR implementation. The real CSR objectives are the company's efforts to contribute the community for sustainable development.

For the effort of PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) in carrying out its CSR program, the company also received an award from the Ministry of Environment and Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia on March 5, 2016, in the category "Producer Initiative Award in Waste Reduction." The award was handed over by the Minister of Environment, Dr. Ir. Siti Nurbaya Bakar and the Vice President of the Republic of Indonesia, H. Muhammad Jusuf Kalla to VP. Corporate Secretary of PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Grup), Leila Djafaar at Celebes Convention Center, Makasar, South Sulawesi

Ethics in business and company sensitivity to the public interest are certainly the main things in the implementation of CSR programs. If the company is less sensitive to its environment, then this allows public resistance to the company. Indeed the company should consider CSR as part of the public rights that must be fulfilled. But Frynas (2009) identifies that the implementation of CSR programs is part of a reason to meet the demands of internal and external interests of the company which include: 1) To comply with a regulation, law and rules 2) As part of a company's social investment to get a positive image 3) Part of the company's business strategy 4) To obtain the licenses to operate from the local community 5) Part of the company's risk management to reduce and avoid social conflicts.

It needs to be understood that CSR programs are sustainable activities and not merely ceremonial. Furthermore, CSR programs should have a real impact both on the people involved and become subjects in CSR activities. Thus, CSR does not only benefit the recipient but the company and the environment in which the company also operates benefits in the long run.

Based on this background, the researcher is interested in examining how CSR implementation is carried out by PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) through the Scavenger Empowerment activities in South Tangerang. In addition, this research is expected to provide inspiration and become a role model for companies that will implement CSR programs based on empowerment of the community to create the sustainable development. Academically, this research is expected to be a reference for further research, and enrichment of the scientific field of communication, especially Public Relations, on how to implement CSR programs by involving the community.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Corporate Social Responsibility

CSR definition is varied. Essentially, CSR is a committed business operation not only to increase the financial profit of the company, but also to build the social economy, holistically, institutionally, and sustainably. Some other names being identical to CSR are corporate giving, corporate philanthropy, corporate community relations, and community development (Zukhruf and Irawan, 2018).

The same opinion was also stated by Kotler and Lee (2005) that CSR is part of a company's commitment to improving the condition of society for the better through discretionary business practices and the contribution of company resources. In this definition, Kotler and Lee emphasize discretionary components, which can be interpreted as volunteerism of companies in implementing business practices that benefit the welfare of society (Irawan, 2018: 116)

Referring to this definition, CSR can be interpreted as a commitment of the organization or company in contributing a form of social responsibility to the community to create the expectations of stakeholders, especially the community in realizing sustainable development and improving the welfare of the community or recipients of CSR programs. Essentially the long-term orientation of a CSR program is the realization of sustainable development.

The sustainable development includes three policy matters, i.e., economic development, social development, and environmental protection. John Elkington in the triple bottom line chart to create the pillars of development, namely "people, planet, and profits" which are development goals 1) The responsibility of the company to maintain environmental capacity to support the sustainability of life for the next generation (planet), 2) The form of corporate responsibility to shareholders (profit), 3) The presence of companies should provide benefits to stakeholders and the wider community (people), and 4) The sustainable development should be supported by a balanced commitment between economic, social and environmental (the sustainability development) (Rachman et al., 2011: 11)

In addition, the benefits of doing CSR can also make the company's reputation considered good, and the public has the trust of the company and its products. Building consumer loyalty based on ethical values that are applied by each company is different from one another, thus forming a difference and becoming a brand characteristic based on the adopted values (Wardhani, 2011: 143).

Various researches show that CSR programs play an important role in shaping cognitive responses, attitudes, and behaviors from stakeholders who have different interests. CSR programs are also found to increase purchase intentions for customers, grow positive appreciation from customers, strengthen customer loyalty, and increase customer trust in the company. In addition, the implementation of CSR programs can also attract potential employees and increase employee commitment and pride towards the company. Furthermore, the implementation of CSR can also influence investors' decisions and preferences by increasing the company's trust. Indirectly, the implementation of CSR programs has benefits as well as the aim of increasing reputation and strengthening the company's competitive advantage in the long run (E Arikan et al., 2016: 132).

2.2 Role of PR in CSR Programs

Public Relations has an important role internally and externally in CSR activities. Basically, Public Relations is an internal and external public. Internal public includes company and employee management. While the external public is the community around the company, government, press, consumers, competitors, agents, and distributors. These publics are very influential in the company.

Conceptually CSR is part of PR. Previously, PR activities aimed at forming and maintaining relationships with the community were called community relations and community development. PR activities through CSR are specifically for communities that need assistance in developing their performance and empowerment through various CSR pillars, such as pillars of education, economy, environment, human resources, security, health, culture, religion, and others (Ardianto, 2011: 1). However, in its implementation in the field, the concept of public relations in CSR activities needs to be interpreted in more detail based on the communication process and model that will be implemented in the implementation of CSR programs. This needs to be considered that giving the communication model implemented by the initiator of the CSR program will have an impact on the level of community participation in the CSR program.

The communication process of Public Relations through CSR activities preferably uses a balanced two-way communication model. This model is able to solve and avoid conflict by improving public understanding to build mutual understanding of support and benefit all parties. This aims to develop and maintain the company's reputation and image to the public. Therefore, in the CSR program, there is always an aspect of how to convey the message to the community.

2.3 The Concept of Community Participation and Empowerment

A sustainable CSR program can be realized when participatory community involvement occurs. Thus, the community that is the target of CSR programs should be the subject of development is a necessity, and this

can be realized through the principle of community empowerment. Community empowerment can be done through the learning process so that the ability to have access and control in development. Through this empowerment, the community is expected to have the ability to seize opportunities for available resources. In addition, the community is able to play a role as a decision maker and determinant in choosing and utilizing these opportunities.

In the other word, we need to understand what is meant by empowerment. Mc Ardle explained that empowerment is a decision-making process by people to achieve collective goals independently through the accumulation of knowledge, skills and other resources in order to achieve their goals without relying on external help. In various countries, Craig and Mayo further explained that many countries showed great attention to the strategy of community participation as a means of accelerating the development process. Therefore, it is necessary to emphasize the increase in the importance of alternative approaches in the form of development approaches that are initiated by the empowerment process (Irawan, 2018: 117)

The success of development based on community empowerment is very close to community participation. Craig and Mayo stated that participation is an important component in generating independence and the empowerment process. The process is done cumulatively so that the more skills a person has, the better the ability to participate. Paul further stated that empowerment and participation are very potential strategies in order to improve economics, social, and cultural transformation. This process will eventually be able to create a development that is people-centered. An international agent, the World Bank, for example, believes that the participation of people in the third world is an effective means of reaching the poorest people to be able to live independently (Irawan, 2018: 117)

3. RESEARCH METHODS

The method that used in this study is a qualitative method with a single case study design. The single case study has three rationalizations, namely: first, when the case states an important case in testing a well-compiled theory, second, the cases present an extreme or unique case and the third is the case of disclosure (Yin, 2011: 46). The uniqueness of the CSR program carried out by PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group), i.e., the implementation of CSR programs that refers to environmental issues and integrated scavenger empowerment. Thus, two problems are resolved, the environmental problem and the economic improvement of the scavengers. The study tries to observe, understand and analyze the implementation of the program.

Data collection techniques are interviews and observations with relevant sources and related to CSR activities conducted by PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group). In addition, the researcher also collects data through field observations. This research is supported by secondary data obtained from offices, books, (literature) or other parties that provide data that is closely related to the object and purpose of the study. The data taken are data containing information value related to CSR activities carried out by PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group), from websites, books, documents, photos and etc.

The selection of resource persons in this study used purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling is a sample determination technique with certain considerations. For example, doing research on the quality of food, a sample data source is a person who is a food expert. This sample is more suitable for qualitative research, or studies that do not generalize (Sugiyono. 2004: 124). Selected speakers are PT CSR Coordinator, Tirta Investama (AQUA Group), Technical Implementer of CSR PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group), EMP Public Relations, and the people involved in CSR programs on the meranti islands.

Data analysis techniques according to Miles and Huberman include three concurrent activities: data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing (verification) (Irawan, 2018: 118). Then to determine the validity of the data, the researcher conducted triangulation techniques. Triangulation is a data checking technique that utilizes something other than research data for checking purposes or as a comparison. Denzin distinguishes four types of triangulation as examination techniques that utilize the use of sources, methods, investigators, and theories (Irawan, 2018: 118). The triangulation technique used in this study is a triangulation of data and sources. Through this technique, the researcher compares the results of interviews with supporting data, then to triangulate the sources, the researcher compares and checks the degree of confidence of the information obtained by: (1) comparing observational data with data from interviews (2) comparing the consistency of the source answers, namely by comparing what the resource person said in public for example, with what was said personally (3) comparing one's perspective, with other people in the work team.

4. DISCUSSION

The CSR program implemented by PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) is the company's commitment and concern for environmental conditions that are increasingly polluted by various kinds of garbage, especially plastic waste. Therefore in 2010 PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) organizes CSR programs based on scavenging fundraising. This CSR program was introduced to the public with the name of *Pemulung* Empowerment Program (PEP).

This *Pemulung* Empowerment Program (PEP) is focused on empowering scavengers, where scavengers have positions in the bottom of the recycling industry, simultaneously they play an important role in the development of the recycling industry in Indonesia. AQUA through PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) developed the *Pemulung* Empowerment Program (PEP) in the South Tangerang area, which is first located in the village of Maruga, Pamulang, South Tangerang.

The CSR program implemented by PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) aims to empower scavengers, improve their welfare while reducing the environmental impact caused by packaging waste. In 2013-2014 scavengers who partnered and joined the *Pemulung* Empowerment Program (PEP) were quite numerous. Through this program, it is expected that it can improve the welfare of the Scavenger community's life through CSR programs and reduce the impact on the environment due to the rate of increase in production carried out and planned, accompanied by an increase in energy consumption and greater environmental impact.

The reference to the implementation of the CSR program in the form of the *Pemulung* Empowerment Program (PEP) is the environmental policy of "Water Ground Policy" which is a guideline in managing the environment. One of these policies in compliance with applicable environmental regulations. The *Pemulung* Empowerment Program (PEP) is also expected to be able to overcome the risk of packaging waste, by making waste management efforts.

In addition to referring to the environmental policy of the "Water Ground Policy," which serves as a guideline in managing the environment through this *Pemulung* Empowerment Program (PEP), Law (UU) number 40 of 2007 concerning Limited Liability Companies and Law No. 25 of 2007 concerning Investment. In addition, specifically for State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs) has also issued a separate regulation which requires SOEs to set aside 2-3% of net income for the Partnership and Community Development Program.

PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) chooses scavengers because in practice they are a part that is not being considered but has a big impact, especially on the environment. *Pemulung* as the spearhead, if there are no scavengers, garbage from the results of community consumption activities does not process it. So that it has a bad impact on the environment and humans themselves. This Empowerment Program Scavenger Program (PEP) covers the establishment of South Tangerang Scavenger Cooperative, Recycling Business Unit (RBU)/ now renamed Reksa Buana Utama, namely plastic packaging recycling business, Healthy Post, health education, free health check consultation with doctors every Thursday at the RBU Cipeucang location, computer training and bookkeeping, BPJS health insurance for families of RBU employees, periodic counseling for RBU and Cooperative employees, Family Gathering, healthy food once a week.

Theoretically, the *Pemulung* Empowerment Program (PEP) program implemented by PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) contains the concept of Triple Bottom Line. One indicator of the success of CSR by implementing the concept is the achievement of sustainable development. CSR programs are not merely distributing money. Moreover, CSR is oriented towards shareholders, stakeholders, and the planet. The concept of profit is a form of responsibility that must be achieved by the company, even the mainstream of the economy which is used as the philosophical footing of the company's operations. But not only profit is a priority, but companies also fulfill their responsibilities to other aspects such as people and planet in order to achieve the sustainable development.

The concept of sustainable development by PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) is in accordance with Goel's (2010) opinion that sustainable development is part of an effort to fulfill the needs of the current generation without sacrificing the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. The method used is trying to integrate three pathways: economics, social, and environmental (Alhaddi, 2015). It is clear that the implementation of the *Pemulung* Empowerment Program (PEP) is oriented towards sustainable development that seeks to balance benefits, natural sustainability, and community empowerment. In addition, the application of the triple bottom line concept is part of the responsibility for future generations.

This is in line with the objectives of PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) in implementing CSR namely realizing waste collectors is not only prosperous economically but also socially, so that scavengers will have competitiveness both locally and nationally in the field of human resources, environment, health, education and supported by conducive investment conditions. This means that aspects of the triple bottom line such as economics, natural and human resources aspects are the focus of the implementation of this CSR.

The program implementation is certainly formulated and based on the company's vision and environmental policy of "Water Ground Policy" so that the CSR program is not carried out only to fulfill an obligation, but the call and movement of the company's conscience. This CSR program is a manifestation of the company's vision to empower scavengers, improve their welfare while reducing the environmental impact caused by packaging waste.

The principle of **profit** is achieved through the empowerment of scavengers and then developed in the Recycling Business Unit (RBU) program located in South Tangerang. The Recycling Business Unit (RBU) is a social model of plastic packaging recycling business where employees work to manage packaging bottles into chunks which then become raw materials for creative items such as t-shirts and other plastic products. The principle of **people** is achieved by increasing the ability of scavengers to add value to the waste they have collected. Thus the waste can be of selling value. In addition, scavengers are also involved in cooperative activities, gaining more understanding in developing their economy. The principle of the planet is achieved by proper waste management, so the volume of waste can be reduced and can minimize pollution in the soil.

Through seriousness and earnest efforts from PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group), produced encouraging results in which the *Pemulung* Empowerment Program (PEP) received an award from the Ministry of Environment and Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia on March 5, 2016, which presented the AQUA Group's Producer Initiative Award in Waste Reduction. This award was handed over by the Minister of Environment, Dr.Ir.Siti Nurbaya Bakar and the Vice President of the Republic of Indonesia, H. Muhammad Jusuf Kalla to VP. Corporate Secretary of PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group), Leila Djafaar at the Celebes Convention Center, Makasar city, South Sulawesi.

When a company implements CSR with a commitment, the company will get various benefits from the CSR program. Another opinion strengthens the argument that there are many benefits that the company will get from CSR activities, which will ultimately build brand quality and strengthen consumer loyalty. This is as stated by Dixon (2004) that corporate performance represents their commitment to stakeholders, the natural environment, and their respective economic benefits. As efficiency and innovation increase, including the presence of this CSR concept, it can generate profits that create competitive advantage and in turn lead to its own profitability, without compromising the environment, the company's attention to social problems can reward their brand for the community and loyalty.

AQUA Lestari is an umbrella for sustainable corporate social responsibility (CSR) programs. PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) provides environmental preservation programs and community empowerment in industrial operational areas from upstream areas with integrated water resource management, then economic development and community health degrees, as well as downstream development such as education in waste management. Balanced with various other sustainable social programs, all of these initiatives are carried out and developed to ensure the availability of quantity and quality of water that contribute to the development of the quality of life of its stakeholders.

The CSR program through the *Pemulung* Empowerment Program (PEP) carried out by PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) refers to DANONE's commitment to environmental protection (planet), improving human health (people), and encouraging the community's economy (profit). Therefore, to achieve this policy, this company conducts CSR activities that have an impact on the community and the environment, and the economic empowerment of the community, in this case, is scavengers.

The *Pemulung* Empowerment Program (PEP) has essentially implemented a comprehensive empowerment process, whereby self-empowerment is a decision-making process by people to achieve collective goals independently through the accumulation of knowledge, skills and other resources in order to achieve their goals without relying on external help. In various countries, Craig and Mayo further explained that many countries showed great attention to the strategy of community participation as a means of accelerating the development process. Therefore, it is necessary to emphasize the increase in the importance

of alternative approaches in the form of development approaches which are initiated by the empowerment process (Irawan, 2018: 117). Referring to the concept, it is clear that the *Pemulung* Empowerment Program (PEP) is oriented to self-sufficient scavengers by providing appropriate understanding and capabilities to scavengers.

To ensure that the *Pemulung* Empowerment Program (PEP) is going well, it requires intervention from communication practitioners, especially public relations to be involved in communicating this program on an ongoing basis and can continue to get the benefits. Through public relations practitioners, the implementation of CSR must be based on credible communication principles that have the context of sustainability, accountability, transparency, materiality, completeness, and responding to the interests of stakeholders.

Conceptually, CSR is part of PR. In a company, public relations activities that aim to form and maintain relationships with the community are called community relations and community development. In this context, CSR is part of the media to build good communication with the community and society through various CSR pillars, such as pillars of education, economy, environment, human resources, security, health, culture, religion, and others (Ardianto, 2011: 1). However, in its implementation, the concept of public relations in CSR activities needs to be interpreted in more detail, given the communication model applied by the initiator of the CSR program will have an impact on the level of community participation in the CSR program. In addition, through the right communication design, the CSR program can also support the strengthening of the company's reputation.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

5.1 Conclusions

The results of the study showed that the *Pemulung* Empowerment Program (PEP) as a CSR program of PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) aims to empower the scavenger economy, but still, pay attention to environmental aspects. The things that can be concluded in this study are: firstly, the CSR program implemented by PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) is a commitment to fulfill the company's moral obligations, strengthen reputation, as a form of company compliance with the prevailing laws and regulations, as well as the company's steps to maintain sustainable business, secondly, the implementation of CSR programs refers to the triple bottom line concept, including achieving profit by realizing the Recycling Business Unit (RBU) and Formation, achieving people by empowering through professional waste management training, achieving the planet with the proper waste management process so that the volume of waste and environmental pollution can be reduced, thirdly, the CSR programs of PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) has a positive impact on the community and the environment; this is evident from the award given by the Ministry of Environment and Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia on March 5, 2016, in the category of "Producer Initiative Award in Waste Reduction."

5.2 Suggestions

Based on the findings, the researcher suggests that the company should consider the following: firstly, increasing community participation in CSR programs is very important, meaning that in the future PT. Tirta Investama (AQUA Group) needs to design CSR programs collaboratively by involving wider stakeholders, not only scavengers but the general public is involved, secondly develop communication models and strategies that are more targeted at the general public, so that the success of CSR programs can be broader. In addition, it is necessary to add various communication and socialization media that can expand the implementation of CSR, and thirdly maintain the consistency of the existence of cooperatives, so that these cooperatives can be more developed in accelerating the economic welfare of members, especially scavengers.

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